

Extent of Teachers' Utilization of Pedagogical Approaches

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Abstract

Pedagogical approaches refer to the various methods and strategies that educators use to facilitate learning and teaching. With the educational trends and development, the researchers conduct this study to assess the extent of utilization of pedagogical strategies – inquiry-based, integrative, collaborative, constructivist and reflective. This is conducted to the grade school teachers of St. Paul University Surigao where total population sampling was applied. A modified survey questionnaire was used to assess the extent of utilization of pedagogical strategies and the data gathered were analyzed using frequency count and percentage distribution, mean and standard deviation, and analysis of variance. It was found that the teachers highly utilized the pedagogical approaches. In addition, the respondents' age, sex, highest educational attainment, length of service and subject/s taught do not influence their utilization of pedagogical approaches. Thus, it is recommended for the teachers to continue utilize the pedagogical approaches to ensure effective teaching-learning engagement.

Keywords: *approaches, pedagogy, teachers, utilization, survey.*

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Introduction

Effective pedagogy, the art and science of teaching, can significantly impact student outcomes, including academic achievement and personal development. Pedagogy encompasses the study of teaching strategies and how they influence students (Main, 2021). Educators employ a wide range of pedagogical approaches, or teaching methods and strategies, to facilitate learning and impart knowledge.

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In the Philippines, the educational system has undergone a dynamic transformation, equipping teachers with a diverse array of strategies and approaches. These enable educators to fulfill their roles as knowledge providers, helping students become adaptable, creative, globally minded, and cooperative. Importantly, learners are encouraged to develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are essential for authentic education.

Research from Malaysia's Sultan Idris Education University has evaluated teachers' approaches in teaching Contemporary Children's Literature, highlighting both the challenges faced and the potential for enhancing students' language learning (Mustakim et al., 2014). This underscores the need for creative and effective pedagogical strategies to optimize educational outcomes.

In the local context, a study by San Jose and Galang (2015) explored the teaching strategies used by AB English teachers in literature courses. The research revealed the prevalence of the lecture-discussion approach as an effective strategy, while emphasizing the importance of adapting teaching methods to address students' diverse learning skills.

Further studies have found that utilizing innovative pedagogical strategies, such as inquiry-based, integrative, collaborative, constructivist, and reflective approaches, can help students clearly understand their lessons and engage with the discussions (Carag, 2020). These strategies place the students at the center of the teaching-learning process, guided by the teacher's expertise.

It is widely recognized that the integration of technology in the classroom can greatly benefit students. The media is being watched, techniques are being developed, tactics are being communicated, and knowledge needs to be obtained. Educators have a responsibility to impart both conceptual and factual knowledge, and they have a variety of tools at their disposal to ensure the teaching-learning process is effective and to monitor the quality of learning outcomes.

In light of these insights, the researchers aim to assess the extent of utilization of these pedagogical strategies – inquiry-based, integrative, collaborative, constructivist, and reflective – among grade school teachers at St. Paul University Surigao. The findings of this study will inform future enhancements in curriculum and instructional delivery, ultimately contributing to the transformation of student outcomes.

Materials and Methods

The study employed quantitative descriptive research using survey technique. This design is deemed appropriate because it provides a detailed and accurate picture of the characteristics and behaviours of a particular population or subject (Sirisilla, 2023). This study was conducted to the 21 Grade School teachers at St. Paul University Surigao during the School Year 2023-2024. A modified questionnaire from Carag (2020) was used in assessing the extent of utilization of pedagogical strategies – inquiry-based, integrative, collaborative, constructivist and reflective. Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution, mean and standard deviation, independent samples t-test and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used in analyzing the data gathered.

Results

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents. As to the respondents' *age*, there are 7 (33.33%) belong to the 23-25 years old bracket, 6 (28.57%) belong to the 29-31 years old bracket, 4 (19.05%) belong to 26-28 years old bracket, 2 (9.52%) belong to 38-40 years old bracket, and one (4.76%) for 32-34 years old and 41-43 years old brackets. As to respondents' *sex*, 14 (66.67%) are females while 7 (33.33%) are males. As to the *highest educational attainment*, 10 (47.62%) have MA units, 9 (42.86%) are baccalaureate degree holders, and 2 (9.52%) are master's degree holders. As to the length of service, 9 (42.86%) served for 4-7 years, 4 (19.05%) served for 0-3 years, 2 (9.52%) served for 16-19 and 24-27 years, and one (4.76%) served for 8-11 years, 12-15 years, 20-23 years and 28 years and above. As to the subject/s taught, 6(18.75%) are teaching English and Math, 5 (15.63%) are teaching Science, 4 (12.50%) are teaching Filipino and MAPEH, 3 (9.38%) are teaching Religion and Araling Panlipunan, and one (3.13%) is teaching EPP.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Profile Variables	f (n=21)	%
Age		
23-25 years old	7	33.33
26-28 years old	4	19.05
29-31 years old	6	28.57
32-34 years old	1	4.76
38-40 years old	2	9.52
41-43 years old	1	4.76
Sex		
Male	7	33.33
Female	14	66.67
Highest Educational Attainment		
Baccalaureate Degree	9	42.86
with MA units	10	47.62
Master's Degree	2	9.52
Length of Service (in SPUS)		
0-3 years	4	19.05
4-7 years	9	42.86
8-11 years	1	4.76
12-15 years	1	4.76
16-19 years	2	9.52
20-23 years	1	4.76
24-27 years	2	9.52
28 years and above	1	4.76
Subject/s Taught		
Religion	3	9.38
English	6	18.75
Filipino	4	12.50
Math	6	18.75
Science	5	15.63
EPP	1	3.13
AP	3	9.38
MAPEH	4	12.50

Pedagogical Approaches Used by the Grade School Teachers

Table 2. Pedagogical Approaches Used by the Grade School Teachers

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Inquiry-Based			
I give activities that are problem-posing to the learners.	3.57	0.75	Highly Utilized
I allow learners to ask questions both to their groupmates and to me.	3.81	0.40	Highly Utilized
I give the learners access to various sources of information to explore ideas and form questions.	3.81	0.40	Highly Utilized
I let learners draw conclusions and revisit the conclusions by asking questions.	3.81	0.40	Highly Utilized
I allow learners to explore which lead to more questions.	3.81	0.40	Highly Utilized
Average:	3.76	0.47	Highly Utilized
Integrative Strategies			
I immerse the learners into differing disciplines to learn a given lesson.	3.71	0.46	Highly Utilized
I allow learners enhance themselves through holistic approach.	3.67	0.48	Highly Utilized
I provide mechanisms for learners to see the connections of their lesson with other subject matters and disciplines.	3.67	0.48	Highly Utilized
I provide scenarios where students arrive with life-related conclusions.	3.90	0.30	Highly Utilized
I pose problems that make learners see the problem in different perspectives.	3.71	0.46	Highly Utilized
Average:	3.73	0.44	Highly Utilized
Collaborative Strategies			
I employ activities that relies heavily on group work among students.	3.33	0.80	Highly Utilized
I allow learners to acquire knowledge from themselves and their peers.	3.86	0.36	Highly Utilized
I let learners review and reflect on their learning processes together.	3.90	0.30	Highly Utilized
I use the prior knowledge of the students to advance their knowledge	3.90	0.30	Highly Utilized
I make sure that learners work in teams through brainstorming and buzz sessions	3.76	0.44	Highly Utilized
Average:	3.75	0.44	Highly Utilized
Constructivist Strategies			
I give tasks to the learners to produce or create new knowledge based on the lesson prepared for them.	3.81	0.40	Highly Utilized
I consider the socio-cultural background of the learners in the discussion of their lesson.	3.71	0.46	Highly Utilized
I allow the learners to use their own “schema” in resolving issues.	3.62	0.59	Highly Utilized
I make sure that learners create and produce an output based on how they interpret situations.	3.81	0.40	Highly Utilized
I give freedom for the learners to arrive at their own thinking of given situations.	3.76	0.44	Highly Utilized
Average:	3.74	0.46	Highly Utilized
Reflective Strategies			
I allow learners to control their own learning process by reflecting on their personal experiences	3.81	0.40	Highly Utilized
I create situations where learners feel safe questioning and reflecting on the processes.	3.81	0.40	Highly Utilized
I employ group discussions where learners are brought to critically think about a given situation.	3.86	0.36	Highly Utilized

I allow learners to talk about what they learn together.	3.81	0.40	Highly Utilized
I let learners provide insights on what they learned in the form of realizations.	3.95	0.22	Highly Utilized
Average:	3.85	0.36	Highly Utilized

Table 2 shows the pedagogical approaches used by the Grade School Teacher in which from the table above, it is learned that in the Inquiry Based strategy among the five indicators, the item *I allow learners to ask questions both to their groupmates and to me, I give the learners access to various sources of information to explore ideas and form questions, I let learners draw conclusions and revisit the conclusions by asking questions and I allow learners to explore which lead to more questions* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}$ = 3.81, SD = 0.40) which can be verbally interpreted as Highly Utilized. This finding underscores the importance and effectiveness of fostering a learning environment that encourages questioning, exploration, and critical thinking among students, ultimately enhancing their engagement and understanding of the subject matter.

However, item *I give activities that are problem-posing to the learners* got the lowest mean ($\underline{M}$ = 3.57, SD = 0.75), which can be verbally interpreted as Highly Utilized. This suggests that suggests that while problem-posing activities are being utilized, there may be room for further emphasis and implementation of this aspect within the Inquiry-Based approach. On average, the Inquiry Based strategy used by the Grade School teacher is verbally interpreted as *Highly Utilized* ($\underline{M}$ = 3.76, SD = 0.47).

In the Integrative strategy among the five indicators, the item *I provide scenarios where students arrive with life-related conclusions* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}$ = 3.90, SD = 0.30) which can be verbally interpreted as highly Utilized. This result suggests that teachers are highly effective in creating scenarios that enable students to draw conclusions relevant to real-life situations. Providing learners with opportunities to connect their learning to practical, real-world contexts is a key aspect of Integrative teaching strategies. As mentioned by Abechuela (2014), integrative teaching involves "well-organized strategies anchored in real-life situations that include student interests and needs.

However, item *I allow learners enhance themselves through holistic approach and I provide mechanisms for learners to see the connections of their lesson with other subject matters and disciplines* got the lowest mean ($\underline{M}$ = 3.61, SD = 0.48), which can be verbally interpreted as Highly Utilized. Although still interpreted as "Highly Utilized", this item suggests areas for potential improvement in the implementation of Integrative teaching strategies. Integrative learning emphasizes the importance of making connections across disciplines and applying critical thinking to real-life problems. By providing mechanisms for learners to recognize the interconnectedness of their lessons with other subject areas and disciplines, teachers can help students develop a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter and its relevance to their overall education and future endeavors. On average, the Integrative strategy used by the Grade School teacher is verbally interpreted as *Highly Utilized* ($\underline{M}$ = 3.73, SD = 0.44).

In the Collaborative strategy among the five indicators, the *I let learners review and reflect on their learning processes together and I use the prior knowledge of the students to advance their knowledge* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}$ = 3.90, SD = 0.30) which can be verbally interpreted as highly Utilized. This suggests that teachers are highly effective in creating opportunities for students to engage in collaborative reflection on their learning and in building upon their existing knowledge.

However, item I *employ activities that relies heavily on group work among students.* ($\underline{M} = 3.33$, $SD= 0.80$), which can be verbally interpreted as Highly Utilized. This suggests that while teachers are effectively incorporating collaborative elements into their instruction, there may be room for further emphasis on structuring activities that rely more heavily on group work. Effective collaborative learning requires carefully designed group activities that promote positive interdependence, individual accountability, and the development of social skills (Main, 2021). On average, the Collaborative strategy used by the Grade School teacher is verbally interpreted as *Highly Utilized* ($\underline{M} = 3.75$, $SD= 0.44$).

In the Constructivist strategy among the five indicators, the I *I give tasks to the learners to produce or create new knowledge based on the lesson prepared for them and I make sure that learners create and produce an output based on how they interpret situations* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}=3.81$, $SD= 0.40$) which can be verbally interpreted as highly Utilized. This suggests that teachers are highly effective in providing opportunities for learners to construct new knowledge through tasks and activities that encourage creative interpretation. Constructivist learning theory emphasizes the importance of learners actively constructing their own knowledge through experiences and reflections. By giving learners tasks that require them to produce or create new knowledge, teachers can foster this process of knowledge construction.

However, item I *allow the learners to use their own “schema” in resolving issues.* ($\underline{M} = 3.62$, $SD= 0.59$), which can be verbally interpreted as Highly Utilized. This suggests that while teachers are effective in providing opportunities for learners to use their own schema, there may be room for further emphasis on this aspect. On average, the Constructivist strategy used by the Grade School teacher is verbally interpreted as *Highly Utilized* ($\underline{M} = 3.74$, $SD= 0.46$).

In the Reflective strategy among the five indicators, the item *I let learners provide insights on what they learned in the form of realizations.* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}=3.95$, $SD= 0.22$) which can be verbally interpreted as highly Utilized. This suggests that Grade School teachers place a strong emphasis on encouraging learners to reflect on their own learning experiences and share their insights.

However, item *I allow learners to control their own learning process by reflecting on their personal experiences, I create situations where learners feel safe questioning and reflecting on the processes and I allow learners to talk about what they learn together* ($\underline{M} = 3.81$, $SD= 0.40$), which can be verbally interpreted as Highly Utilized. These strategies encourage learners to take an active role in their learning, reflect on their experiences, feel comfortable questioning and discussing the learning process, and engage in collaborative reflection with their peers. On average, the Reflective strategy used by the Grade School teacher is verbally interpreted as *Highly Utilized* ($\underline{M} = 3.85$, $SD= 0.36$).

Table 3. Summary Table

Strategies	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Inquiry-Based	3.76	0.47	Highly Utilized
Integrative Strategies	3.73	0.44	Highly Utilized
Collaborative Strategies	3.75	0.44	Highly Utilized
Constructivist Strategies	3.74	0.46	Highly Utilized
Reflective Strategies	3.85	0.36	Highly Utilized
Average:	3.77	0.43	Highly Utilized

Table 3 reveals the summary of the extent of utilization of pedagogical strategies by the teachers. As presented in the table, all the strategies were highly utilized by the teachers (M=3.77, SD=0.43). Specifically, among the five strategies, the *reflective strategies* got the highest mean (M=3.85, SD=0.36) which can be interpreted as *highly utilized*. This means that the teachers employed activities that gave the learners the opportunity to critically think about the given situation and allowed them to process their learning by reflecting on their experiences. In this strategy, teachers continuously introspect and critically analyze their own teaching strategies, beliefs, and assumptions to improve their instructional methods and student learning outcomes (Shah, 2023).

However, the *integrative strategies* got the lowest mean (M=3.73, SD=0.44) which can be interpreted as *highly utilized*. Despite being the lowest, the teachers still highly utilized this strategy by immersing learners in different disciplines and providing them with activities that would allow them to connect with other subject matters and disciplines. This strategy is also important in the 21st century era of education as it allows learners to view learning as interdisciplinary. Integrative learning and teaching strategies, as defined by Baird and Perkins (n.d.), refer to approaches that emphasize the interconnectedness of different areas of knowledge and seek to promote a deeper, more comprehensive understanding of a problem by integrating different perspectives and disciplinary approaches.

Difference in the Extent of Utilization of Pedagogical Strategies when Grouped According to Profile Variables

It can be gleaned from Table 4 that there are no significant differences in the extent of utilization of pedagogical strategies used by the teachers namely *inquiry-based* (p-value=0.366), *integrative* (p-value=0.599), *collaborative* (p-value=0.678), *constructivist* (p-value=0.697), and *reflective* (p-value=0.677) when grouped according to their age. This means that regardless of the respondents' age, they are utilizing the pedagogical strategies. However, in the study conducted by Pranoto et al. (2021), they found that teachers' experiences and ages can impact their teaching performance, with older teachers potentially experiencing a decline in performance as they age. On the other hand, Umanilo (2021) found no significant relationship between age and teaching performance.

Table 4. Difference in the Extent of Utilization of Pedagogical Strategies when Grouped According to Age

Strategies	F	p-value	Interpretation
Inquiry-Based	1.18	0.366	Not significant
Integrative Strategies	0.75	0.599	Not significant
Collaborative Strategies	0.63	0.678	Not significant
Constructivist Strategies	0.60	0.697	Not significant
Reflective Strategies	0.63	0.677	Not significant

It can also be seen from Table 5 that there are no significant differences in the extent of utilization of pedagogical strategies used by the teachers namely *inquiry-based* (p-value=0.117), *integrative* (p-value=0.660), *collaborative* (p-value=0.922), *constructivist* (p-value=0.801), and *reflective* (p-value=0.906) when grouped according to their sex. This means that regardless of the respondents' sex, they are utilizing the pedagogical strategies. This is in contrast with the conclusion of Alnahdi and Schwab (2023) where

they found differences in teaching style and practices based on gender. However, Roallos (2022) concluded in his study that there is a significant relationship between the highest educational attainment and the utilization of pedagogical approaches.

Table 5. Difference in the Extent of Utilization of Pedagogical Strategies when Grouped According to Sex

Strategies	t	p-value	Interpretation
Inquiry-Based	-1.64	0.117	Not significant
Integrative Strategies	0.45	0.660	Not significant
Collaborative Strategies	-0.10	0.922	Not significant
Constructivist Strategies	-0.26	0.801	Not significant
Reflective Strategies	0.12	0.906	Not significant

Table 6. Difference in the Extent of Utilization of Pedagogical Strategies when Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Strategies	F	p-value	Interpretation
Inquiry-Based	1.27	0.304	Not significant
Integrative Strategies	1.96	0.169	Not significant
Collaborative Strategies	1.91	0.177	Not significant
Constructivist Strategies	1.21	0.321	Not significant
Reflective Strategies	0.58	0.571	Not significant

As presented in Table 6, there are no significant differences in the extent of utilization of pedagogical strategies used by the teachers namely *inquiry-based* (p-value=0.304), *integrative* (p-value=0.169), *collaborative* (p-value=0.177), *constructivist* (p-value=0.321), and *reflective* (p-value=0.571) when grouped according to their highest educational attainment. This means that the utilization of the strategies does not depend solely on the highest educational attainment of the teachers. This result is consistent with that of Aquino et al. (2021) where they found that the teachers' performance is irrespective of educational achievement or significant contributions.

Table 7. Difference in the Extent of Utilization of Pedagogical Strategies when Grouped According to Length of Service

Strategies	F	p-value	Interpretation
Inquiry-Based	1.96	0.140	Not significant
Integrative Strategies	0.58	0.763	Not significant
Collaborative Strategies	0.58	0.764	Not significant
Constructivist Strategies	0.59	0.753	Not significant
Reflective Strategies	0.44	0.862	Not significant

Table 7 presents the significant difference in the extent of utilization of pedagogical strategies when grouped according to *length of service*. Findings revealed that there are no significant differences in the strategies used by the teachers namely *inquiry-based* (p-value=0.140), *integrative* (p-value=0.763), *collaborative* (p-value=0.764), *constructivist* (p-value=0.753), and *reflective* (p-value=0.862) when grouped according to the respondents' length of service. This means that whether the teacher has been serving for a longer or short period of time, he/she is implementing or utilizing the pedagogical strategies for the benefit of the learners. The result concurs with Graham et al. (2020)

where they found no evidence that Beginning teachers (0–3 years’ experience) were less competent than teachers with more years of experience. Similarly, there is no difference in teaching performance based on the teachers’ experiences (Pranoto et al., 2021). Umanailo (2021) also found no significant relationship between teaching experience and performance.

Table 8. Difference in the Extent of Utilization of Pedagogical Strategies when Grouped According to Subject/s Taught

Strategies	F	p-value	Interpretation
Inquiry-Based	0.18	0.837	Not significant
Integrative Strategies	0.37	0.695	Not significant
Collaborative Strategies	0.29	0.748	Not significant
Constructivist Strategies	0.40	0.678	Not significant
Reflective Strategies	0.13	0.879	Not significant

Table 8 shows the significant difference in the extent of utilization of pedagogical strategies when grouped according to *subject/s taught*. It can be gleaned from that table that there are no significant differences in the strategies used by the teachers namely *inquiry-based* (p-value=0.837), *integrative* (p-value=0.695), *collaborative* (p-value=0.748), *constructivist* (p-value=0.678), and *reflective* (p-value=0.879) when grouped according to the subject/s taught by the respondents. This means that the area or discipline that the teacher teachers do not influence his/her implementation of the pedagogical strategies.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings gathered, it was concluded that the teachers highly utilized the pedagogical strategies namely inquiry-based, integrative, collaborative, constructivist, and reflective strategies. Moreover, the respondents’ age, sex, highest educational attainment, length of service and subject/s taught do not matter when it comes to their utilization of pedagogical approaches.

It is hereby recommended for teachers to further incorporate integrative strategies, as it had the lowest mean, into their teaching practices to enhance overall effectiveness. Given that reflective strategies received the highest mean, the teachers may continue to promote and support reflective practices.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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